

Vachika Abhinaya As A Tool To Evoke Rasa In Bharatanatyam – With Special Reference To Ragas

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Abstract:

This research explores the symbiotic relationship between Raga and rasa, specifically focusing on Vachika Abhinaya within the context of Bharatanatyam. Emphasising the integral role of music, particularly the seven musical notes, the paper underscores the significance of ragas in Carnatic Classical music, serving as a foundation for the evocation of rasa. Each raga's unique emotional quality contributes to a better understanding of Vachika Abhinaya, thereby enhancing the dancer's bhava. Drawing from Natyasastra, chapters dedicated to music under Vachika Abhinaya, the paper sheds light on the communicative partnership between dancer and musician. The qualitative method has been employed to interview musicians and understand how to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application of music in dance, thereby offering insights to Bharatanatyam practitioners on utilising appropriate ragas to convey specific emotions. Addressing the crucial support role of music, the research highlights the potential barrier posed by a lack of musical knowledge for Bharatanatyam dancers. It emphasises the need for clarity in dance music and proposes a method to empower dancers to communicate their artistic vision effectively. This concise paper serves as a valuable resource for Bharatanatyam artists, providing a deeper understanding of the interplay between ragas and emotions. By decoding the language of music, the research aims to highlight the importance of Vachika Abhinaya through the element of Raga, and enhance the overall expressive quality of Bharatanatyam performances, facilitating a beautiful, musical experience between dancers and spectators.

Keywords: Raga, Rasa, Vachika Abhinaya, Bharatanatyam, Emotions

Introduction

Bharatanatyam is recognized as one of the most renowned Indian classical dance styles. Previously known as *Sadir*, *Dasiattam*, or *Nautch*, it was rebranded as Bharatanatyam almost seven decades ago and has been gaining popularity across the globe ever since. The life breath of all Indian classical dance forms, including Bharatanatyam is *Abhinaya*, and as per the *Natyashastra* authored by Sage Bharata, there are four types of *Abhinaya*, *Angika Abhinaya*, *Vachika Abhinaya*, *Aharya Abhinaya* and *Satvika Abhinaya*. Together, these are commonly referred to as *Chaturvidha Abhinaya*. The magic of an Indian classical dance performance is experienced when there is a perfect blend of the four abhinayas. In Bharatanatyam all the four abhinayas play a vital role, but this paper will lay emphasis on the role of *Vachika Abhinaya* and will highlight the importance of music, and discuss how the rendition of a raga plays a pivotal role in establishing the essence of the dance. Whether it is through vocal or instrumental accompaniment, the dancer relies on exceptional music to establish the ambiance and build a surreal experience for both themselves and the audience. This surreal experience is the final goal of *Natya* i.e *rasōtpati*, as explained in the shloka below:

na hi rasādr̥te kaścīdarthaḥ pravartate |¹

Vachika comes from the root word ‘*Vak*’ in Sanskrit, referring to speech. The mode of communication using speech, dialogue, language, regulation of the tone of voice, etc. is referred to as *Vachika Abhinaya*. “The speech content in a Sanskrit play

¹ Ghosh, Manmohan. *Natyasastram*, Vol. II. Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan Varanasi, Oriental Publishers, 2016. VI.32

can be divided into two parts; *vak* or the spoken word and *gana* or the sung word” (Srinivas, 27). *Vak* comes from words, and words are based on vowels and consonants. In the Indian theatrical forms, both speech and music are of great importance, but in Indian classical dance forms, music takes the upper hand. In Bharatanatyam, music is of great importance, and the entire music ensemble too forms an integral part of Vachika Abhinaya. They have the capacity to add to the expressional element of the dance form to bring out *Rasa*. “The word *Rasa* itself which primarily means 'taste' or flavour metaphorically refers to the emotional experience of beauty in poetry and drama.” (Raghavan). The term *Rasa* is derived from the word ‘*Rasah*’ which literally means ‘sap’ or ‘juice’ or ‘taste’. At an etymological level, *rasa* means the essence, nectar or juice of a performance. According to the *Natyashastra*, the objective of any art form is to evoke *Rasa*, the aesthetic enjoyment within the mind and heart of the cultured spectator. This paper is an attempt to highlight the importance of *Ragas* in bringing out the *rasa* in *Natya*. A *raga* is a combination of *svaras* set to a melodic framework. In the *Natyasastra* there are chapters that have specifically been allocated to music, and in this, Sage Bharata (the author) begins by laying emphasis on the seven *svaras* (musical notes), as below:

Sadjascha Rshabaschiva gaandhaaro madhyamastatha |

*Panchamo dhaivataschiav nishadah sapta cha svarah ||*²

The seven notes are : *Sadja (Sa)*, *Rishaba (ri)*, *Gandhara (ga)*, *Madhyama (ma)*, *Panchama (pa)*, *Dhaivata (Da)* and *Nishada (ni)*.

These seven notes form the basis for any music that is heard in the world. Bharatanatyam is accompanied by Carnatic Classical music, and is accompanied by

² Ibid XXVIII.21

Ragas. The arrangement of svaras in a particular pattern defines the raga, and there are hundreds of ragas in Indian Carnatic music derived from 72 parent or Janaka ragas.³

Each of these ragas have the quality to communicate a particular emotion, and form an integral part of vachika abhinaya, to help the dancer express better. An important function of music is its capacity to communicate emotions⁴ and Bharatanatyam banks on this to a large extent. The combination and understanding between dancer and musician is of extreme importance. Apart from the beauty of voice, clarity is necessary in dance music so that audiences hear and comprehend each word of the song⁵.

Vachika abhinaya serves as a means for the dancer to express the character they embody in their performance. The synchronisation and mutual comprehension between dancer and musician hold immense significance. In music which is used to accompany dance, it is really important for every word of the song to be heard and understood clearly by the audience. This plays a pivotal role in evoking emotions among the audience, enabling them to deeply connect with and resonate with each lyric sung or raga hummed. The dancer aims to harness this ability to foster a profound connection with the audience with the help of Vachika Abhinaya. The accompanying musical ensemble plays a crucial role too in helping the dancer immerse themselves in the character's emotions and overall mood, aiding in conveying the intended message. Understanding how the music and dance work together is crucial as they complement each other in conveying the theme.

³ Kumar, Vijay, et al. "Identifying Ragas in Indian Music." Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition, 2014, doi: 10.1109/ICPR.2014.142.

⁴ Ambika. "Natyabhinaya: The Technique of Abhinaya and Its Application in Sanskrit Drama." University of Madras, Department of Sanskrit, 1995.

⁵ Ghosh, Manmohan. Natyasastram, Vol. II. Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan Varanasi, Oriental Publishers, 2016. VI.32

A lack of musical knowledge acts as a barrier to many Bharatanatyam dancers. When the dancers choreograph movements, they have a certain idea in which the music should flow, and usually, it is choreographed in such a way that it flows according to the raga, and the manner of its rendition. When dancers are unable to communicate what they have in their minds to the musicians, they feel handicapped and helpless. Music is a support system for dance, and aids in the effective communication of the mood that the dancer wishes to translate to the audience. This 'support system' should be supporting the dancer and not confusing their thoughts. A good understanding of ragas will help dancers understand and choreograph the piece differently. This paper will be an attempt to bridge this gap, and aid dancers to understand the use of ragas to bring out certain emotions. In this work, the author aims to use the action method where the researcher and the practitioners collaborate and arrive on the findings.

Related works

The study of emotions and music have been attempted by many researchers.⁶ In the study of emotion perception for Indian classical raga music Mathur et al. dealt with identifying raga association with distinct emotional musical appeal and studied the effect of tempo variations on different emotion perceptions.⁷ The study of emotional response in Hindustani raga music and the connections of emotions with north Indian music were explored by Kirane, Mangaonkar, Joshi, and Kirane⁸. The study of identifying emotions through a particular raga, by trained and untrained musicians, was conducted by Kumar, Pandya, and Jawahar. In this study on identifying ragas in Indian

⁶ Harrison, Peter M. C., editor. Proceedings of the 10th International Conference of Students of Systematic Musicology (SysMus17), London, UK, September 13-15, 2017

⁷ Mathur, Avantika, et al. "Emotional Responses to Hindustani Raga Music: The Role of Musical Structure Rectified." *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 6, 2015

⁸ Kirane, N., Mangaonkar, Namita Joshi, and Nikita Kirane. "Identifying Emotions through Raga: An Exploratory Study," 2014.

music, from the numerous ragas, it was concluded that it is not easy to identify the raga heard.⁹ A study on understanding the nuances involved in a raga, to support a Bharatanatyam performance has not been dealt with in depth. This paper looks at highlighting the importance of Vachika Abhinaya as a tool to generate rasa using ragas.

Raga and Rasa

The word Rasa itself which primarily means 'taste' or flavour metaphorically refers to the emotional experience of beauty in poetry and drama.¹⁰ The concept of 'Rasa' stands as the most crucial and substantial contribution to aesthetics. The eight rasas mentioned in the Natyasastra are *Sringara*, *Hasya*, *Karuna*, *Veera*, *Adbuta*, *Bebatsya*, *Roudra* and *Bhayanaka*. In later texts there was an addition of the *Shanta rasa*, thereby totalling to nine, under the name of *Navarasa*. Without Rasa there is no objective for any of the performing arts. In music, raga plays a huge role in evoking the rasa, and in Bhartanatyam it is through the medium of Chaturvidha Abhinaya that the dancer evokes rasa. One of the four abhinayas, Vachika Abhinaya, will be understood here through the element of music.

The mood-creating component of music is Raga. Ragas can be categorised based on when they are played or the moods they evoke. The emotional essence of a raga, known as *raga-bhava* or mood, determines the anticipated atmosphere or experience for listeners that the raga generates. Past studies have investigated *ragas* and have shown that distinct ragas elicit distinct emotions(Valla et al.). Expressing this mood in words is challenging, often considered a subjective and personal experience, but can be largely bracketed under the eight bhavas. Rasa are created by bhavas

⁹ Kumar, Vijay, et al. "Identifying Ragas in Indian Music." Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition, 2014

¹⁰ Ambika. "Natyabhinaya: The Technique of Abhinaya and Its Application in Sanskrit Drama." University of Madras, Department of Sanskrit, 1995

therefore it is vital to study the eight bhavas, and see how certain ragas elicit rasas from these eight bhavas mentioned in the Natyasastra.

1. Sringara (Rati Bhava)

Shringara, considered the paramount among the navarasas, is defined by Bharata Muni in the Natya Sastra as the Rasa evoking love and beauty. It encompasses romantic love, eroticism, infatuation, attraction, and beauty, symbolising the essence of life, the purpose of creation, and the celebration of humanity. The *Sthayi Bhava* is *Rati* and the *Vibhavas* are the *Nayika* and *Nayaka*, Scenic beauty, youth, seasons, gardens, garlands, ornaments, solitude, listening to songs, fragrance, lovemaking, full moon, breeze etc. The *Anubhavas* are Gentle smiles, frowning, side glances, felicitous movements, graceful movements of limbs, brow, cheeks, soft speech, etc. The types of Sringara are:

- a. Rati Sringara (Love between the hero and heroine)
- b. Vatsalya Sringara (Love between the mother and child / Parental love)
- c. Bhakti Sringara (Love between the devotee and God)

Sringara can be analysed by using the ragas *Kalyani*, *Hamir Kalyani*, *Behag*, *Reetigowla*, *Maand*, and *Surutti*. These are a few ragas that would be appropriate to render for a sringara composition. Of course, the type of sringara has to be assessed, and based on that the raga will be selected and appropriately used. The play of *gamakas* is important, and must be used accordingly in the raga to evoke different types of sringara.

For instance, In *Rati* Sringara, it is essential to use melodious and fluid *gamakas* and phrases. The phrases should be sung in a manner that seamlessly connects all the notes within the specific emotional context through diverse

gamakas. Additionally, the swara patterns should demonstrate up and down wave-like movements.

An important aspect of Rati Sringara is *Viraha*. In this instance, the lower notes of the raga have to be in more prominence. The separation aspect is well portrayed through elongated / *kampitha gamaks* in whichever raga is used. In Bhakti sringara, it is similar to Rati but the bhakti is highlighted when the notes are slower in middle and octave notes, and the sahitya is accordingly rendered. In Vatsalya, it is slightly different. The incident being portrayed should be in the forefront. For eg. if Yashoda is feeding Krishna, then a lilting rendering of the raga is preferred, but if it's a playful incident, eg. Krishna is running away from mother Yashoda after doing some mischief, then the raga needs to be rendered via fast paced dhatu swara notes which have a very frolic appearance in the raga patterns.

2. Hasya (Hasa Bhava)

This Rasa connects to humor, laughter and happiness. The *Vibhavas* Unseemly dress, missing ornaments, covetousness, quarrel, Pointing out the faults of others, etc. The *Anubhavas* are biting the lips, throbbing of the nose and the cheek, opening the eyes wide, contracting the eyes, perspiration, etc.

The types of Hasya are:

3. Atmastha (self-based)
4. Parastha (based in others)

Hasya can be analysed using ragas like *Kadhanakuthuhala*, *Mohanam* and *Bilahari*. To bring out Hasya, there is a strong usage of *Kampitha Gamaka*. The rendition is not very fast nor very slow, it is medium-paced. It oscillates

mainly between two or three notes to create repetitiveness in the swara patterns which will be apt for comedy. Based on the type of hasta the raga should be rendered. These ragas sound positive and can also sound sarcastic at the same time, so it would be apt to use *Vakra Prayogas* in ragas which have consonant notes.

5. Karuna (Shokha Bhava)

Karuna Rasa is the sentiment of compassion or empathy. The *Vibhavas* are curse, distress, downfall, calamity, and separation from the near and dear ones, loss of wealth, etc. The *Anubhavas*, are tears, parched throat and mouth, drooping of the limbs, gasping for breath, loss of memory, etc.

Karuna can be depicted using ragas like Simhendra Madhyama and Keeravani. The Ragas which have Kakali Nishada and Chatushruthi rishaba and Sadharana gandhara are an ideal combination to portray karuna very well. Shuddha Madhyama is an apt swara for Shokha. For eg. In the raga Simhendramadhyamam, 'Ma' doesn't have a specific position, and doesn't have a stance of its own, it's completely dependent on the Panchama. These beautifully bring out the element of *shokha*.

6. Veera (Utsaha Bhava)

As the name suggests, Veera derives its essence from a state of heightened energy. The Rasa comes to life when there exists courage, heroism, expertise, pride, and unwavering resolve. Veera Rasa epitomises a dynamic, resolute nature that leaves no space for astonishment or indecision. The *Vibhavas* are challenging words and deeds conveying courage, boldness, bravery, and self-confidence. The *Anubhavas* are opening the eyes wide and

expanding the nose. It includes physical valour as well as the strength of character. The types of Veera are:

- a. Dana Veera: (By donating or giving gifts)
- b. Daya Veera (Sympathetic to all irrespective of class or creed)
- c. Yudha Veera (Courageous, bold and brave by fighting in a war)

Veera is analysed using the ragas *Kamboji*, *Shankarabharanam* and *Vasanata*. The rendition of the raga is in fast paced , middle to high-pitched notes. The choice of the manner of portrayal of veera should be very specific. The emphasis on the *Jeeva svaras* and *gamakas* should be very specific. The notes should have sharp edges, and the *gamakas* should be crisp. The rendition of the raga must be made with emphasis on certain notes by giving minimal *gamakas*.

7. Bhayanaka (Bhaya Bhava)

This is the emotion of fear. Fear can be caused in different people due to different reasons. The *Vibhavas* are terrific noise, at the sight of something scary like ghosts or ghastly sights, staying in an empty or secluded house, death, etc. The *Anubhavas* are trembling of the hands and feet, hair standing on ends, change of voice and tone, etc.

Bhayanaka is aroused by ragas like *Revathi*, *Rasikapriya* or any other *Vivadi Raga*. Vivadi ragas are where the notes are very close to each other, so that it creates a dissonance, thereby bringing out Bhayanaka bhava in the raga. The emphasis in the rendition is laid on the Vivadi svaras. For eg. *Shatsruthi Rishabam & Antara Gandhara*, in Rasikapriya (the notes are very close to each other).

8. Roudra (Krodha Bhava)

Roudra is the emotion of Anger. The *Vibhavas* are Abuse, insult, speaking lies, Harsh words, jealousy, etc. The *Anubhavas* are red eyes, profuse perspiration, biting of the lips, throbbing of the cheeks, flaring of the nostrils, etc.

Roudra can be demonstrated with the help of ragas like *Pantuvarali*, *Hamsanandi* and *Chandrakouns*. The three main notes used to evoke Roudra are *Shudha Rishabam*, *Shudha Daivatam* and *Prathi Madhyama*: a combination of these can be an excellent portrayal of Roudra. For the portrayal of Roudra, emphasis is laid on *Shuddha* svaras, and on the rendition of Prati Madhyama. Another important point is that the rendition of repetitive patterns of the same svaras in the higher octave is especially conducive with roudra rasa.

9. Adbhuta (Vismaya Bhava)

Adbhuta rasa depicts the feeling of wonderment and is referred to as the “marvellous sentiment”. The *Vibhavas* are the fulfillment of a desire, seeing magical tricks and creations of things beyond imagination, etc. The *Anubhavas* are wide eyes, horripilation, tears, shouts of ha-ha, etc.

Adbhuta can be analysed through ragas like *Attana*, *Kannada*, *Arabhi* and *Nagaswaravali*. All of the mentioned ragas will have one or two notes which have a subtle push element thereby creating a surprise component thereby adding Adhbuta. The svaras in these ragas have a lot of distance between the notes, and *Dhattu svaras* are very prominent in this. While rendering, the emphasis is on one particualr swara which is the jeeva swara which creates adbutha

10. Bebatsya (Jugupsa)

Bibatsa Rasa depicts the odious sentiment, or the feeling of disgust. The vibhavas are seeing something unpleasant, hearing, seeing and discussing something that is undesirable, etc. The *anubhavas* are squeezing the limbs, rolling eyes, vomiting, expressing disgust, etc.

This can be portrayed through ragas like *Saveri* and *Mayamalavagowla*. Typically to bring out the element of disgust a combination of *Shudha Rishabam*, *Shudha Madhyamam* along with either *Shudha Daivatam* or *Chatusruthi Daivatam* rendered in the lower octave is ideal. These notes are elongated and rendered in a lower octave to evoke a feeling of disgust.

Conclusion

Music plays a very crucial role in dance, and it is because of this that dancers are so selective on the music ensemble that accompanies them. The rendition of the ragas, and the mood which they fill the environment with, aids the dancer to stage an unforgettable performance. Through the play of ragas, the entire mood changes, and when these ragas are rendered in the way it has to be rendered, the dancer and the audience have a transcendental experience. The relevance of Vachika Abhinaya is undermined in Bharatanatyam. Each of the compositions in the Bharatanatyam *margas* have numerous ragas and the beauty of the composition is brought out only through the raga.

The rendering of these ragas will get the dancer into a particular mood and help the dancer to evoke a certain rasa. The entire performance is recharged by the play of Vachika Abhinaya. The raga chosen should be integral to dance and needs to be perfectly coordinated with the dancers' movements. That's why understanding music is

essential. When the dancer has enough knowledge to direct the musicians, they play according to the dancer's vision and thereby the expressions are aligned with the dancing, transforming the performance to a new level.

There are so many elements in Vachika Abhinaya that lift the entire environment into a transcendental high and raga is one of them. When the music is going differently and the dancer is doing her own thing, there is only vachika, and there is no abhinaya, but, when the dancer understands a raga and connects with it, Vachika will transform to Vachika Abhinaya, thereby generating rasa.

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